

Huayan School 華嚴宗

also known as “Hua-yen School”

By King Pong Chiu, New Asia Institute of Advanced Chinese Studies

Entry tags: Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Huayan school (huayan zong 華嚴宗), Religious Group, Huayan thought, Chinese Buddhism, Buddhist Traditions

The Huayan School is one of the most important Chinese Buddhist schools in historical China, which mainly prevailed in the medieval period, especially from the 7th to the 9th century. The School is developed from Huayanjing 華嚴經 (Skt. Avataṃsaka Sūtra; Eng. Garland Sūtra), or more precise, the interpretation of Huayanjing from some Chinese monks, and its appearance began in the time of Fazang 法藏 (643–712). In principle, Huayan patriarchs considered their philosophical systems ‘yuan’ 圓, a term, which, to a large extent, implies perfection and finality. From their perspectives, further theoretical development in Buddhism was considered unnecessary, if not impossible, though, in practice, the patriarchs stressed that the achievement of such a perfect and final status needed the help from other Buddhist schools or theories. In this sense, the ‘yuan’ teaching as Huayan School suggested is always all-inclusive. The traditional lineage of the Huayan patriarchs is as below: Dushun 杜順 (557–640), Zhiyan 智儼 (602–668), Fazang, Chengguan 澄觀 (738–839) and Zongmi 宗密 (780–841), and after that the School began to decline. According to Xu gaoseng zhuan 續高僧傳 (Continuation of Biographies of Eminent Monks), Dushun was a Chan master with supernatural power and his relationship with Huayanjing is largely unknown. Interestingly, Zhiyan claimed that his own understanding of Huayanjing was learned from Dushun, which provides the only hint about the potential relationship between Dushun and the Sūtra. In fact, Zhiyan once learned from the masters of the Nan Dilun 南地論宗 and Shelun Schools 攝論宗, the early schools of Consciousness-Only (Skt. Yogācāra; Chi. Weishi 唯識) in China. As Fazang noted, Zhiyan derived his profound understanding of Huayanjing from these masters, which implies a close relationship between Huayan thought and that of Consciousness-Only, though the relationship is observed competitive rather than cooperative. Fazang was called the third patriarch of the Huayan School, but he is actually the real founder of it, as the School began to gain its political and intellectual importance during his time. Fazang once explained his thought to Empress Wu 武后 (624–705) face-to-face around the year 700 and the speech is recorded in Jin shizi zhang 金師子章 (Treatise on the Golden Lion), a short passage which is regarded as a summary of the Huayan thought. After the death of Fazang, however, his disciple Huiyuan 慧苑 (673–743) amended the former’s ideas of doctrinal classification, arguing that certain elements, ‘sudden teaching’ in particular, should be removed from the doctrinal classification theory. This suggestion of Huiyuan was severely criticized by Chengguan, who was later considered the fourth patriarch of the School, and it is from Chengguan that the ideas of Huayan are finalized. The main characteristic of the Huayan thought is its emphasis on non-obstruction and even interpenetration between and among various phenomena. In short, as the Huayan patriarchs argues, the relationship among phenomena as seen from a Buddha perspective is always harmonious and under such harmonization any conflicts among phenomena can be avoided so that different phenomena can eventually co-exist. The key concepts of the Huayan thought, the Dharmadhātu of the non-obstruction of events 事事無礙法界, the Ten Mysterious Gates 十玄門 and the Harmony of Six Characters 六相圓融 for examples, are, to various extents, to explain the rationale behind such harmonization of phenomena. As a matter of fact, Zongmi, the fifth patriarch of the School, used Huayan thought to harmonize Buddhism, Confucianism and Taoism, and this act of harmonization hugely influenced the development of these different intellectual traditions in later China since the 10th century. Despite the significance of the Huayan School, the ‘Huichang Persecution’ 會昌法難, a political movement led by Emperor Wu of Tang 唐武宗 (814–846) in 845, which tried to destroy Buddhism fundamentally, accelerated the fall of the School. Since then, the Huayan School becomes a target of scholarly study rather

than a religious group with real influence in society. Although individual monks in Republican China in the early 20th century tried to promote Huayan thought and make the School reviving, the outcome was in doubt. The situation that the School, if there is any, faces today, is no different from its predecessors in the past thousand years. More effort is definitely needed if development of the School is to be made.

Date Range: 670 CE - 845 CE

Region: Early and early imperial China

Region tags: Asia, China, East Asia

Core area of early and early imperial China

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Jinhua Chen, *Philosopher, practitioner, politician: the many lives of Fazang (643-712)* (Leiden: Brill, 2007).
- Source 2: Guo Cheen, *Translating Totality in Parts: Chengguan's Commentaries and Subcommentaries to the Avatamsaka Sutra* (Lanham: University Press of America, 2014).
- Source 3: Imre Hamar ed., *Reflecting Mirrors: Perspectives on Huayan Buddhism* (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2007).
- Source 1: Robert Gimello, Frédéric Girard and Imre Hamar ed., *Avatamsaka Buddhism in East Asia : Huayan, Kegon, Flower Ornament Buddhism : origins and adaptation of a visual culture* (Wiesbaden : Harrassowitz Verlag 2012).
- Source 2: Peter N. Gregory, *Tsung-mi and the Sinification of Buddhism* (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2002).
- Source 3: Pual Williams, *Mahāyāna Buddhism: the doctrinal foundations* (London and New York: Routledge, 2009).
- Source 1: Steve Odin, *Process Metaphysics and Hua-yen Buddhism: A Critical Study of Cumulative Penetration vs. Interpenetration* (New York: State University of New York Press, 1982).
- Source 2: Wing-tsit Chan, *A Source Book in Chinese Philosophy* (New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1973).
- Source 3: Thomé H. Fang, *Chinese Philosophy: Its Spirit and Its Development* (Taipei: Linking Publishing Ltd., 1986).
- Source 1: Thomas Cleary, *Entry Into the Inconceivable: An Introduction to Hua-yen Buddhism* (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1983).
- Source 2: Francis Cook, *Hua-yen Buddhism: The Jewel Net of Indra* (New York: The Pennsylvania State University Press, 1977).
- Source 3: Garma C. C. Chang, *The Buddhist Teaching of Totality: The Philosophy of Hwa Yen Buddhism* (University Park and London: The Pennsylvania State University Press, 1971).
- Source 1: King Pong Chiu, Thomé H. Fang, Tang Junyi and Huayan Thought: *A Confucian Appropriation of Buddhist Ideas in Response to Scientism in Twentieth-Century China* (Leiden: Brill, 2016).

– Source 2: Erik J. Hammerstrom, *The Huayan University Network: The Teaching and Practice of Avatamsaka Buddhism in Twentieth-Century China* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2020).

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: n/a

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: http://buddhism.lib.ntu.edu.tw/BDLM/sutra/chi_pdf/sutra19/T45n1881.pdf

– Source 1 Description: 法藏, 《華嚴金師子章》, 《大正新修大藏經》 vol. 45, no. 1881.

– Source 2 URL: http://buddhism.lib.ntu.edu.tw/BDLM/sutra/chi_pdf/sutra19/T45n1866.pdf

– Source 2 Description: 法藏, 《華嚴一乘教義分齊章》, 《大正新修大藏經》 vol. 45, no. 1866.

– Source 3 URL: http://buddhism.lib.ntu.edu.tw/BDLM/sutra/chi_pdf/sutra16/T35n1733.pdf

– Source 3 Description: 法藏, 《華嚴經探玄記》, 《大正新修大藏經》 vol. 35, no. 1733.

– Source 1 URL: http://buddhism.lib.ntu.edu.tw/BDLM/sutra/chi_pdf/sutra19/T45n1868.pdf

– Source 1 Description: 智嚴, 《華嚴一乘十玄門》, 《大正新修大藏經》 vol. 45, no. 1868.

– Source 2 URL: http://buddhism.lib.ntu.edu.tw/BDLM/sutra/chi_pdf/sutra19/T45n1886.pdf

– Source 2 Description: 宗密, 《原人論》, 《大正新修大藏經》 vol. 45, no. 1886.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The appearance of the Huayan School in China was complicated, as it happened in the time that the main Chinese intellectual traditions such as Confucianism, Taoism and Buddhism were all prevalent. In this sense, there were unavoidably competitions between and among these intellectual traditions. In fact, both Fazang and Zongmi, the third and the fifth Huayan patriarchs, had learned from Taoist masters and Confucian scholars respectively before they became Buddhist monks. To make the situation more complex, there were also competitions among different Buddhist schools. Therefore, it is seen that there were debates about such topics as the characteristics of Buddha nature, the result of Buddhahood, and the relationships among different theories within the religion. However, as the aim of Huayan thought is to harmonize various values, the competitions between the Huayan School and other religious groups or intellectual traditions seems not serious. It is because the ideal of the Huayan School is never to compete with others, but to solve the potential conflicts among them. In this regard, the Huayan School tries to help different intellectual traditions or religious groups co-exist, rather than put itself into a superior position among its counterparts. In brief, the relationship between the Huayan School and other intellectual traditions or religious groups are both competitive and accommodating, and no simple answer about their relationships could be made.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– I don't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: It seems that the assignation of religious affiliation was mainly decided by the patriarchs and the followers. In short, it is probably an individual conduct and no clear 'official' process or system were found.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– I don't know

Notes: As one of the most influential Chinese Buddhist schools, the Huayan School principally had quite a large number of followers. However, it was probably the philosophical ideas that it attracted the people to join the School, and no other ways for the School to actively recruit members were observed.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: It is famous that Fazang, the third patriarch of the Huayan School, was supported by Empress Wu. To a large extent, the development and prevalence of the School was due to the support of Empress Wu, while Fazang provided his support to Empress Wu in return during the process of Wu's responding to the challenges raised by Confucianism and Taoism related to her status of being the first and only empress in the Chinese history.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– I don't know

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– I don't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: Despite of its influence, the number of adherents of the School is largely unknown, due to the lack of a reliable statistical record.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: It is seen that the masters or the teachers enjoy the highest position in the group.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: According to Xu gaoseng zhuan 續高僧傳 (Continuation of Biographies of Eminent Monks), Dushun, the first patriarch of the School, could forefeel the happenings of earthquakes and have the power to cure the incurable diseases.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– I don't know

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– I don't know

↳ Powers are inherited:

– I don't know

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: The leaders of the School were the masters who taught the Huayan thought to their students. In this sense, the leaders were not chosen but decided by their seniority.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Based on the historical fact, Huiyuan once challenged the views of his teacher Fazang and it was not until the appearance of Chengguan that Huiyuan's points of view were rejected and the status of Fazang was resumed. In this regard, the ideas of the Huayan patriarchs were open to be challenged, as long as the test was based on rationality.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The views as the Huayan School held were also criticized by those from other Buddhist schools, such as the Schools of Only-Consciousness and Tiantai.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: There are quite a lot of scriptures in the Huayan School and the followings are some examples:

- 1.) Zhiyan, Huayan yisheng shixuanmen 華嚴一乘十玄門 (Ten Mysterious Gates of One Vehicle of Huayan)
- 2.) Fazang, Dafang guangfo huayanjing jinshizizhang 大方廣佛華嚴經金師子章 (Treatise on the Golden Lion)
- 3.) Fazang, Huayan yisheng jiaoyi fenqi zhang 華嚴一乘教義分齊章 (An Outline of the Huayan Teaching of the One Vehicle)
- 4.) Fazang, Huayanjing tanxuanji 華嚴經探玄記 (Notes of Searching Mystery of Huayanjing)
- 5.) Chengguan, Dafang guangfo huayanjing suishu yanyi chao 大方廣佛華嚴經隨疏演義鈔 (Advanced Annotation of Huayanjing)

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the scriptures are oral.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: As a member of Buddhism, the Huayan School sticks to the Buddhist concept of śūnyatā or ‘empty’. This idea, on the one hand, admits that there are different phenomena, our bodies included, existing in the world, while, on the other hand, stresses that there are always changes in or for these phenomena. No phenomenon has an unchanged essence. In this regard, our bodies are not only what we actually see now, but also the possible status that they could be. For the Huayan School, it is exactly the possibility for phenomena to change that it allows the various phenomena to coexist as the current conflicts among them are only ‘empty’. To change the perspective to view an issue, our judgment about it will be different and as a result the obstruction could be solved in principle. To some extent, this possibility for phenomena to change is to be considered ‘spirit’ beyond bodies, in which humanity needs to pay effort to further cultivate.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: If body is conceived as appearance and the ‘spirit’ is regarded as ‘empty’ as mentioned above, then there could be difference between the two while the former means actuality but the latter implies possibility, which is waiting for the cultivation of humanity.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As a member of Buddhism, it is strange to say that the Huayan School does not believe in afterlife. However, the foci of the School is always the achievement of harmony in this life. And issue related to afterlife is seldom, if not never, discussed.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Similarly, the issue about reincarnation is not the foci of the School, though, as a member of Buddhism, it should not reject such idea.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Since the Huayan School develops its thought based on its own interpretation of Huayanjing, the issue of 'supernatural being' needs to consider the content of the text. As Huayanjing argues, there are countless lights released from Vairocana, the symbol of Buddha in the Huayan tradition, and these lights reach the other Buddhas and bodhisattvas without difficulties. Furthermore, Huayanjing also mentions that Sudhana, a clever boy who is keen to learn more about Buddhism, once met such bodhisattvas as Mañjuśrī, Samantabhadra and Maitreya. If Buddhas and bodhisattvas are to be regarded as 'supernatural beings', then the Huayan School certainly believes in such beings, though Mahāyāna Buddhism stresses that Buddhas and bodhisattvas are also transformed by ordinary persons.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As described in the Huayanjing, the lights from Vairocana reaches the Buddhas and bodhisattvas in different space and time. In this sense, the Huayan School seems not to deny the existence of previous human spirit.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It largely depends on the definition and understanding of 'mixed human-divine beings'. According to Huayanjing, Vairocana, other Buddhas and bodhisattvas are obviously with certain kinds of divine characteristics. Since Mahāyāna Buddhism suggests that all Buddhas and bodhisattvas are transformed by ordinary persons, Vairocana etc. can be considered 'mixed human-divine beings' in this sense.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It is interesting that, as a major Buddhist school in China, the thought of the Huayan School is widely criticized as too inclusive, as it tends to harmonize all phenomena. Since phenomena with negative values are, to many scholars' understandings, also included in this harmonization, bad deeds seem to be allowed in the Huayan thought. If this understanding is correct, then no general social norms are specifically held by the Huayan School.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Since the Huayan School considers that all phenomena are interpenetrating, no single phenomenon is excluded by the Huayan thought in principle. In this sense, all phenomena can be regarded as ways of practice and no specific way of practice needs to be emphasized particularly. However, the Huayan School stresses that it is only from the perspective of Buddha but not for the ordinary people. As the theories like the Four Dharmadhātus and the Doctrinal Classification Theory suggests, there is always a gradual process that ordinary people need to follow before they develop themselves into Buddhas. Therefore, the Huayan School does admit that time is a necessary condition for followers in their practice, though the time period needed is not specifically mentioned.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Notes: It seems that all adherents of the Huayan School needed to know the texts as written by the patriarchs. In this regard, specific scholarly training did exist within the religious group. In fact, a group of monks tried to revive the Huayan tradition in the early 20th century China and the curriculum is now available. Although there is no necessary relationship about the ways of education between the monks in the modern time and those in the medieval China, the experience of the former is worth mentioning. For more information, see Erik J. Hammerstrom, *The Huayan University Network: The Teaching and Practice of Avatamsaka Buddhism in Twentieth-Century China* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2020).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: It is observed that both Fazang and Chengguan enjoyed great political positions in their times, and interaction between the Huayan School and the officials were obvious.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No